

Assessment of Groundwater Quality and Land use Land-cover in and Around Pondicherry by using Water Quality Index and Remote Sensing Techniques

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Key Points:

- The study shows a decline in water quality from 2015 to 2023, with many areas moving from “Excellent” or “Good” to “Poor” WQI due to rising salinity and contamination from factors like EC, Cl⁻, and SO₄²⁻.
- LULC analysis shows urban expansion, agriculture changes, and vegetation loss drive water resource degradation, especially in Mogaiyur and Kattukuppam.
- The study calls for integrated water management, pollution control, sustainable planning, and community engagement for long-term water sustainability.

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Abstract

This work investigates the relationship between water quality variations and changes in land use and land cover (LULC) in and around Pondicherry between 2015 and 2023. The Water Quality Index (WQI) analysis reveals a substantial decline across multiple locations, with numerous sites transitioning from “Excellent” or “Good” to “Poor” status. Key indicators such as Electrical Conductivity, Chlorides, and Sulphates show increasing trends, highlighting growing salinity and contamination, primarily attributed to urbanization, industrial activities, and agricultural runoff. Concurrently, LULC analysis identifies significant shifts, including urban sprawl, intensified agriculture, and reduced vegetation cover, which collectively contribute to water quality deterioration. Urban expansion, especially around Pondicherry, has led to encroachment on water resources and exacerbated pollution. The observed correlation between declining water quality and LULC changes emphasizes the effect of human interventions on water systems. These findings emphasize the urgency for sustainable water resource management through improved pollution control measures, balanced land-use practices, and community involvement. Proactive conservation efforts in stable regions and focused remediation in areas with persistent poor water quality are necessary to address the escalating environmental challenges effectively.

Keywords: LULC, Water Quality Index, Anthropogenic Activities, Water resource management, Agricultural Activities

1. Introduction

Groundwater is one of the main natural resources that provide drinking water globally (Das and Nag, 2022; Gao et al., 2020). Due to the increasing population and commercial operations the need for freshwater is rapidly enhancing principally in arid, semi-arid, and distant rural areas where groundwater is widely spent for household, agricultural, and potable purposes (Aeschbach-Hertig and

Gleeson, 2012; Makki et al., 2021; Mishra, 2023). During the drought period when the surface water availability is very low, groundwater is highly reliable (Adimalla et al., 2020; Dube et al., 2020).

The surface and groundwater quality can be easily measured by using the Water quality index (WQI) models (Al-janabi et al., 2021). By changing the sequence of data points WQI models represents a unified numerical water

quality scenario (Sutadian et al., 2016). To attain unique goals many countries and groups have created WQI models. Critics of these strategies point to model ambiguity, consistency, clarity, and sensitivity (Uddin et al., 2022a; Uddin et al., 2022c; Uddin et al., 2023b). The WQI models involve four steps: selecting water quality indicators, creating sub-indices, weighting indicators, and aggregating them (Gupta and Gupta, 2021; Uddin et al., 2022b). Uddin and Jeong, 2021 carried out the assessment of different WQI models emphasizing their merits and demerits. Geographical Information Science (GIS) tools have been widely used to visualise the spatio-temporal distribution of water quality status (Kumar et al., 2019; Ram et al., 2021; Sultana and Dewan, 2021; Uddin et al., 2022a; Uddin et al., 2023a; Uddin et al., 2023c).

The physical, chemical and biological process of a watershed can be change due to the impact of LULC. It has also a significant role in the change of surface and groundwater quality. Forest land cover is crucial for sustaining water purity, while urban and cropland areas with excessive fertiliser usage damage water quality (Liu et al., 2016; Wang and Zhang, 2018; Xiao et al., 2016). Improper land management methods have led to a significant loss in freshwater availability and quality (Li et al., 2008). According to Liu et al., 2012, deteriorated water endangers livelihoods and economic viability in addition to causing ecological imbalances in the surface water body. The three primary variables influencing surface water quality, according to researchers, are agriculture, deforestation, and growing urbanisation (Muhammed et al., 2022). Consequently, it has become imperative to monitor and report surface water quality as well as determine how it relates to LULC. In general, monitoring spatiotemporal fluctuations in physical, biological, and chemical signs of water requires water quality analysis (Fashae et al., 2019).

Urbanisation and land use/land cover (LULC) patterns have a major effect on groundwater quality (Brink et al., 2008; Robertson et al., 2017; Subba Rao et al., 2019), particularly in metropolis regions with high anthropogenic activity (Jia et al., 2018; Subba Rao and Chaudhary, 2019). He et al., 2019 suggest a three-step procedure for investigating the relationship between groundwater quality and LULC patterns: (1) quantifying groundwater quality, (2) defining LULC patterns in the study area, and (3) linking the quantified WQI to LULC models.

Depending on the spatial scale the link between LULC and water quality varies (Tanaka et al., 2016) (Tanaka et al., 2016). Recent research in landscape ecology and planning has examined the spatial structure of the landscape to understand the complex interaction between land use and water quality at various levels (Alberti et al., 2007). Landscape patterns influence biogeochemical and physical processes in a watershed. Changes in landscape patterns can impact hydrological processes, including surface runoff and the geochemical cycle, causing contaminants to enter water bodies (Wang et al., 2013). The LULC and landscape pattern analysis can provide valuable indicators of water-quality changes, indirectly reflecting man-made activities and pollutant transfer (Huang et al., 2009; Verburg et al., 2009). Global land use changes are influenced by population expansion, economic development, and higher standard of living, leading to a significant link between LULC and groundwater nitrate levels (Gao et al., 2021; Li et al., 2023). However, LULC expansion is predicted to worsen groundwater depletion and quality degradation (Liaqat et al., 2021; Lindquist et al., 2019). Furthermore, human actions including mining, intensive agriculture, urbanisation, and industrial growth can pollute groundwater (Adimalla and Qian, 2021; Chen et al., 2023; Schwarzenbach et al., 2010). Rapid urbanisation has complicated the interaction between LULC changes and groundwater quality dynamics, offering environmental issues (Acharya et al., 2023; Azizi et al., 2022).

The present work intends to find the relationship between the LULC along with the water quality in and around the Pondicherry. The main objective of the investigation includes (1) explore the variation of the groundwater for past 8 years using Weighted Arithmetic Index method. (2) identify the variations of LULC, in the 8 years using satellite imageries, and (3) analyse the relationship between LULC and water quality.

2. Study Area

Puducherry, formerly known as Pondicherry, is located on the southeastern coast (Coromandel) of India and spans 294 km². It lies between 11° 45'–12° 03' N latitude and 79° 37'–79° 53' E longitudes (Figure 1). This Union Territory includes four non-contiguous districts: Puducherry (293 km²), Karaikal (161 km²), Yanam (20 km²), and Mahe (9 km²). Puducherry and Karaikal are the largest districts, situated amidst Tamil Nadu enclaves, with the

Figure 1: Location Map of the Pondicherry Region.

Bay of Bengal forming their eastern boundary. Puducherry is 162 km south of Chennai, surrounded by South Arcot districts, with a terrain that is largely a peneplain but transitions into mildly undulating uplands, particularly in the northwest and northeast, where elevations reach 30–100 m above mean sea level.

The region is divided into five communes, encompassing 164 villages and the topography includes coastal plains, alluvial plains, and uplands. The coastal plain is a narrow strip along the Bay of Bengal, approximately 22 km long and 400–600 m wide, featuring sand dunes, lagoons, mudflats, and tidal inlets. The alluvial plains, shaped by the Gingee and Ponnaiyar rivers, form a monotonous landscape with a gentle slope of 1–3%. These plains also have depressions serving as natural reservoirs for surface water storage. The uplands, locally known as “Les Montagnes Rouges” or the “Red Hills of Puducherry,” rise between 30 and 100 m amsl and are dissected by gullies and ravines, resulting in uneven terrain.

Geologically, the area is characterized by unconsolidated and semi-consolidated formations overlying an Archaean crystallines. The sediments include clay, limestone, sand, gravel, and sandstone. These formations are classified into two hydrogeological units: fissured crystalline and porous sedimentary formations (Figure 2). Groundwater occurs under phreatic and semi-confined conditions, with wells typically yielding 100–500 liters per minute (lpm). Tube wells, crucial for irrigation and domestic use, can extract up to 2 lakh liters per day in alluvial aquifers. Deeper wells in Tertiary and Cretaceous aquifers, reaching depths of 100–400 mbgl, can yield 1000 lpm using submersible pumps. However, groundwater development has reached 139% (as of 2011), indicating overexploitation. This highlights an urgent need for groundwater conservation, recharge strategies, and sustainable management to protect the aquifers. The regional geological setting of the area is compiled (Table 1).

Puducherry has a tropical climate with hot summers and moderate winters. Summer temperatures range from 24–40°C, peaking at 43°C in May. The region receives most of its rainfall during two monsoon periods: July–September and November–January, with the north-eastern monsoon contributing significantly. Humidity levels remain high year-round due to its coastal location. Win-

ters are cooler, but temperatures rarely fall below 20°C, ensuring a generally warm climate. Land use in Puducherry reveals that 49% of the area is unsuitable for cultivation, consisting of fallow and barren lands, while the remaining 51% is open for groundwater management planning. Agriculture dominates the region, with a large portion of the population engaged as cultivators and farm labourers. Groundwater serves as the primary resource for both irrigation and drinking. Additionally, Puducherry’s status as a popular tourist destination increases the demand for potable water, further stressing groundwater reserves.

Figure 2: Geology of Pondicherry Region.

3. Hydrogeological set up

The Pondicherry, located along the coast, relies heavily on both surface and groundwater resources. Water conservation and efficient irrigation are crucial, as groundwater levels often decline due to limited recharge and high evaporation rates. During the pre-monsoon (PRM), the depth to the water table (DTW) varies from 4 to 8 meters below ground level (mbgl) but can be deeper in coastal areas with excessive groundwater extraction.

Table 1: Regional geologic setting of the area (Modified after Anon1, 1994)

Era	Period	Epoch	Formation	Lithology
Cenozoic	Quaternary	Recent	Alluvium, laterite	Sands, clays, silts, kankar, and gravels, laterite
		Mio-Pliocene	Cuddalore	Sandstone & siltstones with thin seams of lignite
<i>Unconformity</i>				
Cenozoic	Tertiary	Palaeocene	Manaveli	Calcareous siltstones, claystone, shale, limestone
			Kadaperikuppam	Sand, limestone, sandstone, and clays
<i>Unconformity</i>				
Mesozoic	Upper Cretaceous	Thuruvai	Limestone, conglomerate, calcareous sandstone, and clays	
		Ottai Claystone	Claystones, silts, sandy limestone, and calcareous sandstone	
	Lower Cretaceous	Vanur Sandstone	Quartzite sandstone with minor clays	
		Ramanathapuram	Carbonaceous silty clays, sands with bands of lignite and sandstone	
<i>Unconformity</i>				
Archaean			Eastern Ghat complex	Charnockites and Biotite hornblende gneisses

The post-monsoon season (PSM) sees a drop in temperatures and rainfall, creating a more pleasant climate. Agricultural activities increase during this time as farmers utilize residual soil moisture for winter crops. Monsoon rainfall replenishes lakes, rivers, and aquifers, ensuring

adequate water supply for domestic, agricultural, and industrial needs. Groundwater in unconsolidated aquifers, comprising riverine alluvium and floodplain deposits, is extracted using large diameter dug wells and shallow tube wells (25–50 m depth), with DTW during PRM ranging

from 4 to 30.50 mbgl and PSM from 3 to 29.50 mbgl. Tertiary aquifers (25–350 mbgl) and Cretaceous sandstone aquifers (65–400 mbgl) are tapped using tube wells, with yields varying based on depth and formation.

Groundwater in Pondicherry exists in both fissured and porous sedimentary formations, spanning geological periods from Archaean to Recent. In fissured formations, groundwater occurs under phreatic conditions in weathered mantles or semi-confined settings at deeper levels. The thickness of weathered zones ranges from 2 to 12 m, and large-diameter wells can yield 100–500 liters per minute (lpm), running for 2 to 6 hours daily. Porous sedimentary layers dominate the region, comprising Quaternary deposits and partially cemented strata from Cretaceous to Tertiary periods. These include highly productive aquifers like Vanur-Ramanathapuram Sandstone (Cretaceous), Cuddalore Sandstone (Tertiary), and shallow alluvium (Quaternary). Tube wells in Tertiaries of Cuddalore Sandstone, can range from 27 to 366 m in depth and yield between 200 and 3,000 lpm. Cretaceous aquifers of Ramanathapuram and Vanur formations, exhibit varying thicknesses and grain sizes, producing yields of 800 to 1,500 lpm. Groundwater flow rates and aquifer conditions fluctuate seasonally, influenced by geological features and recharge patterns.

4. Methodology

The study is carried out in four steps as depicted in the Figure 3 - (1) Traditional water quality analysis, encompassing laboratory experiments and assessment of temporal variations, (2) Collection and pre-processing of satellite data, (3) Application of the Water Quality Index (WQI) to assess water quality and its changes over different periods, and (4) Investigation of the relationship between LULC pattern and water quality.

Water quality data spanning from 2015 to 2023 was collected from eight well locations in Pondicherry through the Central Ground Water Board (CGWB) SECR, Chennai. The analysis was conducted in a laboratory under controlled conditions following the APHA (2022) guidelines. The data set focused on key cations and anions to evaluate water quality over the years.

Remote sensing data were acquired from the European

Space Agency’s Sentinel-2A mission, which offers high-to-moderate spatial resolution (10–60 m) with 13 spectral bands. These data, freely available through USGS and ESA platforms, provide high accuracy and frequent revisit times of 2–5 days, making them ideal for monitoring water quality. Sentinel-2 images cover a wide swath (290 km) and span visible, near-infrared, and short-wave infrared bands, enabling detailed optical data capture.

In this study, eight key parameters were selected to calculate the Water Quality Index (WQI) based on guidelines recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO), the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS), and the Indian Council for Medical Research (ICMR). The weighted arithmetic index method (Brown et al., 1972) (Brown et al., 1972) was employed to determine the WQI. This method involves two primary calculations: the Quality Rating (or Sub-Index) and the Unit Weight. The equations are provided in Table 2. The classification of the WQI status after (Brown et al., 1972) is compiled (Table 3).

Figure 3: Flowchart of Applied Methods.

Table 2: Equations for calculating WQI.

Step	Formula	Description
Quality Rating (q_n)	$q_n = \frac{V_n - V_{io}}{S_n - V_{io}} \times 100$	V_n : Observed value, S_n : Standard permissible value, V_{io} : Ideal value (0 for most, 7 for pH).
Unit Weight (W_n)	$W_n = \frac{K}{S_n}$	S_n : Standard permissible value, K : Proportionality constant.
Water Quality Index (WQI)	$WQI = \frac{\sum(q_n \times W_n)}{\sum W_n}$	Combines q_n and W_n for a comprehensive WQI index.

Table 3: WQI Classification after Brown et al., 1972.

WQI	WQI Status
0–25	Excellent
26–50	Good
51–75	Poor
76–100	Very Poor
> 100	Unfit for Consumption

ion. This could be attributed to elevated salinity, potentially due to factors like seawater intrusion, pollution, or industrial discharges (Chidambaram et al., 2016; Motevalli et al., 2017). Total Hardness, which is influenced by the concentrations of Ca and Mg, exhibited high variability, particularly in 2017 (mean: 557.8) and 2021 (mean: 432.2), reflecting changes in mineral content, possibly linked to regional groundwater characteristics or treatment changes (Singaraja et al., 2014).

Ca and Mg levels followed similar trends, with the highest Ca concentration observed in 2016 and the highest magnesium values occurring in the years 2017 and 2018, contributing to increased hardness. Chloride concentrations, which are often a result of seawater intrusion or industrial runoff, increased significantly, with the highest mean chloride recorded in 2023 (mean: 253.5). This aligns with the increasing salinity observed in the EC data, supporting the hypothesis of seawater intrusion (Gopinath et al., 2016; Rajendiran et al., 2019). Fluoride levels, while generally stable, peaked in 2022 (mean: 0.9), suggesting local variations, possibly influenced by changes in water source or natural fluorite deposits. Sulphate levels also varied considerably, reaching the highest mean in 2023 (188.4), which could indicate pollution from industrial sources or agricultural runoff (Kazakis et al., 2015). Sodium concentrations, which are a critical factor for water palatability and suitability, showed a gradual decline over the years, but the highest sodium levels were still recorded in 2017 and 2021, further supporting the salinity hypothesis (Fatema et al., 2018).

5. Result and Discussion

5.1. Groundwater Quality

The Table 4 reveals significant trends in the water quality parameters over the years from 2015 to 2023, with notable fluctuations in key indicators like EC, Chlorides, and Sulphates. The pH levels remained fairly stable across the years, ranging from 7.3 to 7.9, which suggest slightly alkaline water, with minimal variation as indicated by the low standard deviation (STD). Such consistency in pH is typical for natural water systems but can be influenced by treatment processes or nearby environmental factors. The EC, a key indicator of ion concentration, showed sharp peaks in 2017 and 2023, with the highest values of 3840 and 4443, respectively, pointing to an increased dissolved

Table 4: Descriptive statistics of the measured water quality parameters.

Parameter	2015				2016			
	Min	Max	Mean	STD	Min	Max	Mean	STD
PH	7.5	9.07	7.9	0.5	6.83	7.59	7.3	0.2
EC	370.0	2480	1420.8	678.6	501	2240	1291.2	582.2
TH	125.0	420	224.4	94.7	105	445	268.9	110.0
Ca	36.0	60	46.4	8.7	24	98	51.1	21.7
Mg	7.3	80.256	26.3	23.9	10.944	71.744	34.3	18.7
Cl	71.0	349	211.6	99.2	42.6	362.1	167.6	108.8
F	0.1	0.78	0.4	0.2	0.3	1.297297	0.6	0.3
SO4	24.0	188	81.5	53.2	57.5	150	99.1	34.0
Na	27.6	274	153.6	91.1	25	228	136.8	60.2
Parameter	2017				2018			
	Min	Max	Mean	STD	Min	Max	Mean	STD
PH	7	7.6	7.4	0.2	6.5	7.5	7.2	0.3
EC	431	3840	1637.1	1040.2	190	4080	2008.6	1296.2
TH	160	860	412.8	198.3	60	920	557.8	307.9
Ca	40	160	96.0	37.6	12	236	124.9	71.2
Mg	9.7216	111.7984	42.0	32.7	7.2912	114.2288	59.7	37.6
Cl	28.36	574.29	237.9	190.0	28.36	864.98	358.8	279.3
F	0.64	1	0.8	0.1	0.04	0.938484	0.6	0.3
SO4	22	720	157.1	227.6	32.16	670	158.2	201.4
Na	23	483	187.2	171.9	15.41	485.3	194.3	159.1

Parameter	2019				2021			
	Min	Max	Mean	STD	Min	Max	Mean	STD
PH	6.4	7.55	7.1	0.4	6.19	8.55	7.9	0.7
EC	510	2380	1370.9	608.7	643	3720	1789.1	1072.7
TH	220	500	380.0	108.7	140	1050	432.2	291.3
Ca	48	126	91.8	27.0	28	300	95.6	84.4
Mg	17	116.6592	47.1	30.5	4.9	88	46.9	27.7
Cl	21	427	216.3	125.3	57	768	290.1	256.8
F	0.2	0.93	0.4	0.2	0	0.53	0.2	0.2
SO4	5.3	140	75.2	45.5	21	274	111.4	94.0
Na	25.2	309	133.3	88.9	46	418	186.1	119.3
Parameter	2022				2023			
	Min	Max	Mean	STD	Min	Max	Mean	STD
PH	6.8	7.61	7.3	0.3	7.04	7.64	7.4	0.2
EC	299	2780	1391.6	697.5	311	4443	1615.1	1088.8
TH	100	560	380.0	147.9	200	1320	557.5	294.8
Ca	24	124	76.4	29.4	48	136	91.5	28.1
Mg	9.7224	87.5016	45.9	26.2	19.4592	243.04	79.9	61.6
Cl	35.45	567.2	191.4	161.9	48.45	1141.4	253.5	321.0
F	0.316958	0.949529	0.6	0.2	0.496958	1.012611	0.7	0.2
SO4	38.4	384	163.2	102.5	50.4	402	188.4	112.5
Na	9.2	374.9	137.0	121.1	37.1	355	142.2	95.6

The data points to a trend of increasing salinity and contamination over time, with specific parameters like EC, Cl, and SO_4^{2-} indicating possible environmental stressor factors like industrial pollution or seawater intrusion. The variability in hardness and metal concentrations could be due to a combination of natural and anthropogenic factors, including water source changes and regional treatment practices. These results emphasise the need for continuous interventions and management to address water quality challenges in the region.

5.2. Analysis Water Quality Changes

The analysis of Water Quality Index (WQI) trends from 2015 to 2023 across multiple locations reveals varying patterns of water quality over time (Figure 4 and Figure 5). Kattukuppam shows a gradual deterioration in water quality, moving from “Good” status in 2015 to “Poor” by 2023. M.N. Kuppam follows a similar trend, with a significant decline from “Good” in 2015 to “Poor” in 2023. Reddichavadi maintained a predominantly “Good” status from 2015 to 2022 but shifted to “Poor” in 2023, indicating a declining trend in recent years.

Villianur exhibits fluctuating trends, with its status oscillating between “Excellent,” “Good,” and “Poor,” while Chinnasalem shows consistent water quality, largely staying in the “Good” or “Excellent” range, except for a few deviations. Gingee 1 displays a noticeable decline in quality, transitioning from “Excellent” in 2018 to “Poor” in 2023. Similarly, Kallakurichi 2 shows a steady drop in WQI, moving from “Excellent” in 2015 to “Poor” by 2023. In Marakkanam, the water quality fluctuates significantly, alternating between “Excellent,” “Good,” and “Poor” status across the years. Mogaiyur demonstrates a consistent “Poor” status from 2017 onwards, with no signs of improvement. Conversely, Siruvadi DW maintains relatively stable water quality, predominantly within the “Good” category, with occasional shifts to “Poor” or “Excellent” status in certain years.

The water conditions across the studied regions appear to reflect significant variability and trends in quality. The data suggests a general decline in water quality over the years in most locations, as evidenced by transitions from “Excellent” or “Good” status in earlier years to “Poor” or “Very Poor” status by 2023. For instance, areas like Kattukuppam and M.N. Kuppam have seen consistent degradation, indi-

cating possible challenges in maintaining water quality. In other locations like Reddichavadi and Villianur, the trends indicate fluctuating water quality, which might point to intermittent issues that temporarily affect water conditions but do not establish a long-term pattern of degradation. Stable water quality is observed in Siruvadi DW, remaining largely “Good,” suggesting better management or favorable conditions in that area. In contrast, locations such as Gingee and Kallakurichi show a steady decline, with the latter deteriorating from “Excellent” in earlier years to “Poor” more recently, reflecting growing challenges in water resource conditions. The persistent “Poor” conditions in Mogaiyur highlight areas where water quality issues are entrenched.

Overall, the prevailing water condition in the region shows signs of stress, with increasing instances of poor-quality water, suggesting a need for improved water management and conservation efforts to address declining trends.

5.3. Changes in Land Use and Land Cover, LULC)

The LULC changes in Villupuram, Cuddalore, and Pondicherry from 2015 to 2023 show substantial trends in a variety of land categories, including agricultural, built-up areas, vegetation, and water bodies as shown in Figure 6.

Agricultural land in these regions has remained relatively stable overall, with notable shifts in intensive farming areas, such as the expansion of double and triple cropping, driven by rising agricultural output demand (Kumaravel and et al., 2014; Rajendiran et al., 2019). However, the area under fallow land has fluctuated, reflecting seasonal and cyclical farming methods, as well as shifting agricultural policy and climate impacts (Chidambaram et al., 2022). The combination of these factors causes both growth and periodic declines in arable land.

The built-up areas, particularly in urbanised places such as Pondicherry, have grown significantly. This expansion encompasses both residential and commercial developments, with urban sprawl encroaching on nearby agricultural and natural environments. Rapid infrastructure growth in metropolitan centres such as Villupuram and Cuddalore, fuelled by population growth and tourism, has resulted in the conversion of large tracts of rural land into urbanised regions (Chidambaram et al., 2022; Kyara and

Figure 4: Variation of water quality indicators in different sampling sites.

Figure 5: Variation of WQI from 2015 to 2023.

Figure 6: Comparison of LULC of 2015 and 2023.

et al., 2021).

Vegetation areas, including woods and plantations, have declined in places experiencing urbanisation or conversion to agricultural land. However, some places have seen initiatives to afforest, particularly in rural or protected areas. Despite these efforts, woodland and shifting cultivation areas are decreasing, often being replaced by agricultural or built-up land (Ferrer and et al., 2019; Gopinath and et al., 2015). The loss of vegetation due to human involvement is obvious, however preservation measures are being implemented in some locations.

Water bodies have changed noticeably because of urbanisation and agricultural operations. Encroachment and drying up of water bodies are visible in some locations, despite continued attempts to protect wetlands and lakes, which represent both natural cycles and the impact of anthropogenic interventions on water resources (Kourgialas and et al., 2017; Prusty and et al., 2018). In conclusion, the LULC patterns in Villupuram, Cuddalore, and Pondicherry demonstrate a delicate balance of agricultural requirements, urban growth, and conservation initiatives, underscoring the continuous difficulty of managing land resources in the face of increasing pressures.

5.4. Correlation among LULC and WQI

The WQI analysis for various locations from 2015 to 2023 reveals significant trends and fluctuations in water quality due to natural and man-made factors. For instance, in Kattukuppam, the WQI indicates a steady decline, transitioning from a “Good” status in 2015 (41.90) to “Poor” in 2023 (50.79), suggesting increasing pollution over time. Similarly, M.N. Kuppam shows a sharp decline, with the WQI worsening from 28.28 (“Good”) in 2015 to 72.67 (“Poor”) in 2023, possibly due to urbanization or industrial activities.

Reddichavadi maintained a relatively stable “Good” status over the years but transitioned to “Poor” in 2023 (53.76), likely reflecting seasonal variations or increased agricultural runoff. Conversely, Chinnasalem largely retained “Good” to “Excellent” ratings, except for a dip in 2017, indicating better water management. Meanwhile, Gingee experienced a steep decline, with its WQI dropping from “Excellent” (7.55) in 2018 to “Poor” (54.94) in 2023, signalling significant environmental stressors like urban sprawl or deforestation.

In Kallakurichi, water quality deteriorated from “Excellent” (19.63) in 2015 to “Poor” (72.39) in 2023, suggesting severe contamination likely tied to industrial or agricultural pollutants. Marakkanam, on the other hand, fluctuated between “Excellent” (14.76 in 2019) and “Poor” (55.41 in 2023), possibly influenced by seasonal factors and urban encroachments. Mogaiyur consistently showed “Poor” water quality from 2017 onward, peaking at 65.77 in 2022, reflecting long-term contamination. Siruvadi DW, however, maintained a relatively stable “Good” status across most years, with occasional dips into “Poor,” indicating effective but inconsistent management efforts.

Overall, these trends highlight the impact of urbanization, agricultural runoff, and industrial activities on water quality. Areas like Kattukuppam and Mogaiyur demand immediate attention for pollution control and wastewater management, while Chinnasalem serves as a model for effective water resource management. High-fluctuation areas such as Marakkanam require regular monitoring and seasonal interventions to maintain water quality. This data underscores the need for sustainable practices, enhanced water treatment infrastructure, and consistent community engagement to preserve water resources.

6. Conclusion

The study gives a broad analysis of water quality and land use patterns from 2015 to 2023, revealing significant trends and interconnections. The WQI data shows a clear trend of deteriorating water quality in most locations, with many transitioning from “Excellent” or “Good” to “Poor” status. This decline is reflected in key parameters such as EC, Cl, and SO_4^{2-} , highlighting increasing salinity and contamination due to natural and anthropogenic stressors. The LULC analysis reveals considerable urban expansion, shifts in agricultural practices, and loss of vegetation, all contributing to changes in water resource conditions. The correlation between LULC changes and WQI trends emphasizes the impact of urbanization, industrial activity, and agricultural runoff on regional water systems. Areas such as Mogaiyur and Kattukuppam are particularly affected, exhibiting consistent poor water quality, while regions like Siruvadi DW showcase relative stability due to effective management practices.

This study underscores the urgent need for integrated water resource management, including pollution control, sustainable urban planning, and community engagement. By addressing the root causes of water quality decline and mitigating the impacts of LULC changes, it is possible to ensure the long-term sustainability of water resources in the region.

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Susan Jacob Reshma - Conceptualization, Investigation and Writing Original Draft. **Joji V.S.** - Data Curation, Visualization, Reviewing and Supervision. **Divya A.S.** - Formal Analysis, Reviewing and Preparation of a few maps.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors do not have any competing interest in terms of financial or personal relationship with a third party whose interests could be positively or negatively influenced by the article’s content. All data used in the study was sourced by the primary and secondary data collection by the first author in connection with the research program.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are collected from the SECR, Central Ground Water Department, Chennai. The data support the findings of this study are available from corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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